

THE BALLISTIC PERFORMANCE OF UK MILITARY HELMETS EXPOSED TO HOT/WET & COLD/WET CONDITIONS.

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ABSTRACT.

The influence of hot/wet and cold/wet environmental regimes on the ballistic performance of the current UK military combat helmet was assessed using Internationally recognised techniques. These conditions were not seen to significantly alter the protection offered from fragmentation threats. However, different mechanisms of failure were observed and these appear to be influenced by the temperature at which the helmets were conditioned rather than the absorbed moisture content.

INTRODUCTION.

The Helmet, Combat, GS Mk 6 is the in-service combat helmet utilised by the UK armed forces. It consists of a nylon 6,6 shell, a high density polyethylene foam liner, suspension harness and chin-strap. The helmet provides protection from both fragmenting munitions, which are the greatest cause of casualties in general warfare, and non-ballistic impacts. The shell is manufactured from nylon 6,6 (945d'tex) woven into a plain weave fabric of mass 290g/m² with 13 x 13 threads per cm. This fabric is pre-impregnated with a phenolformaldehyde-polyvinyl butyral resin (50/50 by weight) and consolidation is achieved in a 200 ton press at 165°C for 20 minutes. The fabric/resin ratio is 80/20 and the areal density of the helmet shell is approximately 7.70kg/m². The helmet was developed at the Science & Technology Division of the Defence Clothing & Textiles Agency (S&TD DCTA) and entered service during the mid to late 1980's. The DCTA is responsible for the research, development, quality assurance and procurement activities for all clothing and textiles utilised by the UK armed forces with the exception of flight crew and diving clothing.

This research project was sponsored by the Ballistic Protection Section at S&TD DCTA and aimed to investigate the influence of hot/wet and cold/wet conditions on the ballistic performance of the Mk 6 shell.

MATERIALS.

Fifteen Mk 6 helmet shells were supplied by S&TD to the research group at the Royal Military College of Science (RMCS). All helmets were from the same batch (10817) and were manufactured in 1985 by Courtaulds Aerospace (Coventry). Since manufacture the helmets had been stored at S&TD in ambient conditions of humidity and temperature. Each helmet shell was assigned a serial number.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEEDURE.**ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONING.**

The dry mass of each helmet shell was recorded before commencement of environmental conditioning. The mass of helmets after conditioning was also recorded. The dry and wet masses and environmental regimes considered are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Environmental Conditioning of Mk 6 Helmet Shells.

Shell identification	Dry mass g	Regime	Wet mass g
A1	1 054.70	As received	N/A
A2	1 096.30		N/A
A3	1 096.30		N/A
B1	1 075.20	Immersion in ambient temperature water for 24 hours	1 076.90
B2	1 075.20		1 079.90
B3	1 057.70		1 059.30
C1	1 080.10	Immersion in ambient temperature water for 24 hours. Conditioned to 45°C for 2 hours.	1 080.70
C2	1 032.80		1 033.30
C3	1 050.10		1 050.80
D1	1 063.70	Immersion in ambient temperature water for 24 hours. Conditioned to -10°C for 24 hours.	1 064.40
D2	1 049.00		1 049.80
D3	1 080.10		1 080.70
E1	1 077.50	Immersion in ambient temperature water for 116 days.	1 087.30
E2	1 066.90		1 077.30
E3	1 080.60		1 089.10

BALLISTIC TEST TECHNIQUE.

The Small Arms Experimental Range (SAER) at RMCS.

Ballistic testing was completed at the 25m indoor small arms experimental range, RMCS. SAER is equipped with two pairs of calibrated electronic digital timers (Materials Technology Instruments) of accuracy 0.001ms. The timers operate on a light beam basis, that is, a penetration of the light beam is detected by a photocell and used to start and stop the timers. One pair of timers is located in front of the target, the other behind it.

Weapon and Ammunition.

The weapon used for testing was a no. 3 bench mounted proof housing, fitted with a 7.62mm rifled barrel and a laser aiming device. Standard 7.62mm NATO ball cartridge cases were loaded with various weights of ICI Nobel propellant NPP 160.

Target Mounting.

A hole was drilled into the crown of each helmet which, during testing, were inverted and bolted to a rigid framework located 10m from the weapon.

The 1.10g Fragment Simulating Projectile (FSP) V_{50} Test.

The ballistic performance of the helmet shells was determined using the 1.10g FSP V_{50} test which is both a UK MOD and NATO standard. The V_{50} is the velocity at which the probability of penetration of a specimen by a stated FSP is 50%. The FSPs are chisel nosed cylinders ranging in mass from 2.79g - 0.16g. The most commonly used FSP has a mass of 1.10g. Three V_{50} values were obtained for each regime and the arithmetic mean and standard deviation were determined.

The test is conducted by mounting the FSP in a lightweight polymeric sabot which then fits into a 7.62mm NATO ball cartridge case. The V_{50} value is the arithmetic mean of three complete penetrations and three partial penetrations of the target. The spread of these six velocities must not exceed 40m/s. All testing was completed within 20 minutes of removal from the conditioning chamber.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS.

ENVIRONMENTAL CONDITIONING.

The intake of water into the nylon 6,6/phenolformaldehyde-polyvinyl butyral structure can be expressed in terms of the mean mass increase for each helmet group. This data is presented in Table 2 and demonstrates that minimal water absorption does occur. This increase in mass was seen to be influenced by length of exposure time, for example, groups B (0.249%) and E (0.890%). Secondary conditioning (to either +45°C or -10°C) was seen to lead to a reduction in absorbed water (compared to no secondary conditioning) and suggests the uptake process is, at least partially, reversible.

Table 2. Water Absorption data for the Mk 6 Shell.

Helmet group	Mean mass increase %
B	0.249
C	0.006
D	0.007
E	0.890

1.10g FSP V₅₀ RESULTS.

The 1.10g FSP V₅₀ data obtained from testing the helmet shells is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. 1.10g FSP V₅₀ Results.

Shell identification	1.10g FSP V ₅₀ m/s	Mean 1.10g FSP V ₅₀ m/s	SD/mean %
A1	411	401	2.14
A2	391		
A3	402		
B1	404	413	1.78
B2	422		
B3	411		
C1	419	417	2.00
C2	426		
C3	411		
D1	403	413	1.68
D2	416		
D3	413		
E1	394	402	1.27
E2	404		
E3	407		

Examination of the S&TD database of V₅₀ values obtained over a number of years has led to the conclusion that V₅₀ figures, for nominally identical materials, are probably normally distributed with a standard deviation of up to 5% of the mean. Considering the data obtained during this research it is possible to conclude that the environmental regimes examined have not significantly altered the 1.10g FSP V₅₀ of the Mk 6 helmet shell (Figure 1). However, it is interesting to note that in this short study, it appears that disruption of the shell structure (by ingress of water) has led to a decrease in the spread of data obtained in each helmet group.

Figure 1. 1.10g FSP V₅₀ Data for Mk 6 Helmet Shells Exposed to Different Environmental Regimes.

MECHANISMS OF FAILURE.

A total of five different failure mechanisms were observed. This discussion considers the macro rather than micro scale observation of these failure mechanisms. They are described by considering the helmet groups in which they appeared.

Helmet Groups A, B and E.

The normal mode of failure witnessed in helmet which were not secondary conditioned is divided into two types, partial and complete. The quantity of absorbed water did not appear to influence this mechanism.

1. Partial - During a partial penetration the FSP is stopped or "captured" by the helmet structure. Fibre failure occurs in the initial strike face layers leading to energy dissipation. At some period of time, the energy becomes insufficient for fibre failure processes and further energy absorption occurs by delamination of the structure. The rear face layers become distorted leading to a behind face effect (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Partial Penetration.

2. Complete - During a complete penetration, the FSP has sufficient energy to cause fibre failure throughout the structure. Fibre pullout is in evidence on the rear face with reduced delamination and distortion compared to a partial penetration. An increased excess energy leads to a penetration with decreased fibre pullout, whereas, a decreased excess energy leads to an increase in delamination and distortion (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Complete Penetration.

Helmet Group C.

Two distinct modes of failure were observed in the helmet group which had been exposed to hot/wet conditioning.

1. Absorption - The material appeared to absorb the FSP with no evidence of fibre failure. However, fibre melting and strike face delamination and distortion due to transfer of material from the FSP were observed. Delamination and rear face distortion were not observed (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Absorption.

2. Acceptance - The FSP penetrates the strike face layers by a process of either fibre failure or fibre melting. Delamination caused by (probably) a combination of flexibilisation of the matrix and the dissipation of the impact energy in the middle layers of the structure provides a path for the FSP which leads to a change in direction of penetration. This process results in a loss of penetration energy and no evidence of delamination or distortion on the rear face (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Acceptance.

Helmet Group D.

After conditioning at cold/wet regimes, the matrix material acted in a more brittle manner. The fabric appeared less affected and strike face penetration was by a process of fibre failure similar to that observed in groups A, B and E. An increased area of delamination and distortion in the rear face and through thickness of the helmet was observed.

CONCLUSIONS.

1. The environmental regimes considered did not significantly influence the 1.10g FSP V₅₀ ballistic performance of the in-service UK military combat helmet.
2. The absorbed water content of the structure did not appear to influence the mechanisms of failure.

3. The temperature at which conditioning occurred was seen to influence the mechanism of failure. Specifically:

- a. At ambient temperatures, FSP energy absorption is by fibre failure and delamination.
- b. At elevated temperatures, FSP energy absorption is by fibre melting and matrix flexibilisation leading to disruption of the FSP path.
- c. At cryogenic temperatures, FSP energy absorption is by fibre failure and increased delamination due to the increased brittle nature of the matrix material.

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